

- 1 **Provide follow-up with continuous healthcare** that starts during pregnancy, encompasses labor and delivery, and continues throughout the postpartum period (beyond the immediate perinatal period).
- 2 **Complement this follow-up with both physical and emotional support**, during the entire evaluation and healthcare period. This is to get to know the mother's general state, to detect both physical and emotional distress, to answer any questions there may be, and to be able to act in a timely manner and according to the needs that arise.
- 3 **Include perinatal psychologists in the pregnancy, labor, and postpartum processes**. For comprehensive follow-up, the number of professionals helping the mother must be increased to ensure her well-being; this includes on an emotional level.
- 4 **Enhance the role of healthcare professionals dedicated to caring for patients, and strengthen the relationship with gynecology and obstetrics professionals**. Physical therapists, midwives, and perinatal psychologists are the main professionals tending to mothers during the postpartum period, and they have first-hand knowledge of the real status of a woman, information which must be communicated to the professionals who helped them during labor and delivery.
- 5 **Properly inform the mother so she can make informed decisions and avoid having false expectations**. When making the birth plan, the route to be taken must be defined. For this to be done with care, the health professionals must inform the mothers about all the scenarios that may unfold, so that these women can be aware of the potential realities ahead of time. Mothers don't want to expect things that later will not happen.
- 6 **Have previous knowledge of the mother**. In order to offer personalized care, the health professional must have a detailed background, beyond that of the medical record: they should be aware of the physical and emotional characteristics of the mother, along with her habits and interests. Mothers want professionals to act with their best interests in mind, treating them as a unique case.
- 7 **Explain to the mother what happened during labor and delivery** to answer questions and explain the reasons why certain things happened, and create a labor and delivery report as a way to bring the process to a close.
- 8 **Compare the birth plan and the labor and delivery report** to identify and understand the changes or unexpected events that happened and, in consequence, increase the risk and may be a trigger for postpartum depression.
- 9 **Personalize follow-up for each mother**. Based on the provisional standard follow-up, adjust the type of follow-up that the mother will receive: how much information she wants to have about what will happen and what has happened, when she wants care, how much care and follow-up she needs, what professional needs to see her, and when.
- 10 **Conclude the follow-up with a complete report on the pregnancy, labor and delivery, and postpartum process**. Throughout the follow-up, the different professionals and mothers will write down their evaluations, the objectives, and the procedure followed in each case, which will allow for continuous information, a vision of the evolution, and ensure that the labor and delivery process is correctly brought to a close.